

An updated checklist of Insecta: Orthoptera of Tamil Nadu with new distributional records

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ABSTRACT

Tamil Nadu has totally about 384 species in the order Orthoptera belongs to the superfamily Acridoidea consists of 2 families, 14 subfamilies, 80 genera and 126 species. The superfamily Pyrgomorphoidea consists of 2 families 2 subfamilies, 13 genera and 35 species. Whereas the superfamily Tetrigoidea consists of only one family under which there are 3 subfamilies, 11 genera and 37 species. The superfamily Grylloidea consists of 8 families, 5 subfamilies, 33 genera and 121 species and lastly the superfamily Tettigonioidea consists of only one family under which 6 subfamilies, 10 genera and 65 species.

Keywords: Insecta, Orthoptera, Tamil Nadu.

INTRODUCTION

Tamil Nadu lies in the southernmost part of the Indian Peninsula and is bordered by the union territory of Pudhucherry and the states of Kerala, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh. It is bound by the Eastern Ghats in the north, the Nilagiri, the Anaimalai Hills and Palakkadu on the west, by the Bay of Bengal in the east, the Gulf of Mannar, the Palk Strait in the south east and by the Indian Ocean in the south. The total area covered by the state is 130058 sq. kms. Of which 22933.79 sq. kms. is under forests. The Eastern and Western Ghats meet in this state and run along its eastern and western borders. The hill of the Western Ghats has dense forests as compared to Eastern Ghats. This region receives maximum rainfall and hence favours plantations of tea, coffee and spices. However, the upper reaches of the Eastern Ghats are not without their share of beauty and Yerkadu in the Shervarayan hills is

famous for its fruit orchards, banana and coffee plantations.

Tamil Nadu has its own natural bio-resources of plants and animals. There are many groups of animals living in the forest covered areas of the state. Among those animal groups the grasshopper is one of the largest and most diverse groups of insects. They are functionally important being the dominant above ground invertebrates in cultivated and natural grassland (Scott *et al.*, 1979; Risser *et al.*, 1981). Some grasshopper cause significant damage to tree seedlings and agricultural crops (Joshi *et al.*, 1999). In India only 1,750 species (nearly 8.75%) of orthoptera have been documented out of 20,000 species found in the world (Somnath Waghmare, Dinesh Waghmare and P. S. Bhatnagar, 2013). Majority of the species are tropical but are also well represented in temperate areas.

Kirby and Chopard are the major contributors in the work on orthoptera in India but so far few data about orthoptera of Tamil Nadu state is available; only some scattered information on faunal diversity of orthoptera of this state has been published by some workers like Bolivar (1900, 1902), Fletcher (1914, 1921), Kirby (1914), Hancock (1915), Hebard (1929), Chopard (1935, 1969), Henry (1937, 1940), Kevan (1952), Kevan and Singh (1964), Muralirangan and Ananthkrishnan (1974), Kesavram (1986), Shrinivasan (1986), Muralirangan, Shrinivasan and Suresh (1992), Ghosh (1996), Chitra, Soundararajan and Gunathilagaraj (2000, 2001), Shishodia and Kulkarni (2001), Karpagakunjaram, Kolatakar and Muralirangan (2002), Ingrisich and Muralirangan (2003), Kandeban, Raguraman, Gunathilagaraj and Ganapathy (2004), Prabakar (2009) and Senthilkumar (2006, 2010). The present work is exclusively for the state of Tamil Nadu and a lot of additions have been carried out. The single Asterisk (*) seen before the species name indicates that the particular species is a pest of agricultural and forestry importance.

SYSTEMATIC LIST

Order ORTHOPTERA

Suborder CAELIFERA

Superfamily ACRIDOIDEA

Family ACRIDIDAE

Subfamily ACRIDINAE

1. *Bababuddinia bizonata* Bolivar, 1918

Distribution: India: Karnataka (Mysuru, Bababuddin Hills) and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Cariola* Uvarov, 1929

2. *Cariola carinata* (Uvarov, 1929)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Tanakamalai in Anaimalai Tiger Reserve).

Genus *Duroniopsis* Bolivar, 1914

3. *Duroniopsis bitaeniata* Bolivar, 1914

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Shervarayan Hills).

Genus *Paraphlaeoba* Bolivar, 1902

4. *Paraphlaeoba carinata* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai).

5. *Paraphlaeoba platyceps* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Coonoor).

Genus *Paraphlaeobida* Willemse, 1951

6. *Paraphlaeobida gracilis* Willemse, 1951

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Perella* Bolivar, 1914

7. *Perella insignis* Bolivar, 1914

Distribution: India: Bihar, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Genus *Zygophlaeoba* Bolivar, 1902

8. *Zygophlaeoba attractocera* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Shervarayan and Yelagiri Hills).

9. *Zygophlaeoba collina* Uvarov, 1929

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri and Yelagiri Hills).

10. *Zygophlaeoba foveopunctata* Bolivar, 1914

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Shervarayan and Yelagiri Hills).

11. *Zygophlaeoba sinuaticollis* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Chennai and Thiruchirappalli).

12. *Zygophlaeoba truncaticollis* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Chennai and Thiruchirappalli).

Tribe **Acridini** Macleay, 1821

Genus *Acrida* Linnaeus, 1758

13. **Acrida exaltata* (Walker, 1859)

Distribution:

India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Iran, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, South East Tibet, Sri Lanka, Yemen and West Aden.

14. *Acrida gigantea* (Herbst, 1794)

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Africa and Nepal.

Genus *Phlaeoba* (Stal, 1860)

15. *Phlaeoba angustidorsis angustidorsis* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

16. **Phlaeoba infumata* Brunner Von Wattenwyl, 1893

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, East Nepal, Hainan Islands, Myanmar, South & North Malacca, South China, Tenasserim and Yunnan.

17. *Phlaeoba panteli* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan.

18. *Phlaeoba rotundata* Uvarov, 1929

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu (Upper Palani Hills, Kodaikanal).

Genus *Phlaeobida* Bolivar, 1902

19. *Phlaeobida angustipennis* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Thiruchirappalli).

Tribe **Truxalini** Serville, 1838

Genus *Truxalis* Fabricius, 1775

20. * *Truxalis indica* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

21. *Truxalis nasuta* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Algeria and northern Africa.

Subfamily **CALLIPTAMINEAE** Tinkham, 1940

Genus *Acorypha* Krauss, 1877

22. * *Acorypha glaucopsis* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Iran and Saudi Arabia.

Genus *Brachy xenia* Kirby, 1914

23. *Brachy xenia scutifera* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Palaciosa* Bolivar, 1930

24. *Palaciosa khandalensis* Bolivar, 1930

Distribution: India: Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **OMMATOLAMPIDINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Tribe **Abracrini** Amédégno, 1974

Genus *Omalotettix* Bruner, 1906

25. *Omalotettix obliquus* (Thunberg, 1824)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Brazil, China, Hunan and Manshan area.

Tribe **Catantopini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Subfamily **CATANTOPINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Castetria* Bolivar, 1902

26. *Castetria dispar* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai).

Genus *Choroedocus* Bolívar, 1914

27. *Choroedocus capensis* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Hainan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

28. *Choroedocus illustris* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

Genus *Coniocara* Henry, 1940

29. *Coniocara rubropicta* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Thirunelveli, Naraikadu).

Genus *Dubitacris* Henry, 1937

30. *Dubitacris robustus* Henry, 1937

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Mopla* Henry, 1940

31. *Mopla gutata* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Naraikadua* Henry, 1940

32. *Naraikadua charmichaelae* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Thirunelveli, Naraikadu).

Genus *Natahanacris* Willemse & Ingrisch, 2004

33. *Natahanacris quadrimaculata* Willemse & Ingrisch, 2004

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu Anaimalai Hills and Cinchona.

Genus *Oxycatantops* Dirsh, 1953

34. *Oxycatantops spissus praemonstrator* (Karsch, 1893)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Africa.

Genus *Pachyacris* Uvarov, 1923

35. *Pachyacris vinosa* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: North Bengal and Tamil Nadu.

36. *Pachyacris violascens* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Palniacris* Henry, 1940

37. *Palniacris maculatus* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Top Slip Camp, Anaimalai Hills).

38. *Palniacris rugulosus* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Pelecinotus* Bolivar, 1902

39. *Pelecinotus brachypterus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

40. *Pelecinotus cristagalli* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai).

Genus *Siruvania* Henry, 1940

41. *Siruvania dimorpha* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Punachimalai and Attakatti).

Genus *Tinnevellia* Henry, 1940

42. *Tinnevellia andrewi* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Thirunelveli, Naraikadu).

Tribe *Oxyrrhepini* Tinkham, 1940

Genus *Oxyrrhepes* Stål, 1873

43. *Oxyrrhepes obtusa* (Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Indo-China, Indonesia, Java, Lombok, Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Catantopides* Ramme, 1941

44. *Catantopides ophthalmicus* (Karny, 1907)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Stenocroblylus* Gerstaecker, 1869

45. *Stenocroblylus femoratus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai).

Genus *Xenocatantops* Dirsh & Uvarov, 1953

46. * *Xenocatantops humilis humilis* (Serville, 1839)

Distribution : India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Borneo, Indo-China, Java, Lombok, Malaysia, Myanmar, New Guinea, Philippines, Sumatra, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Tibet, Vietnam and Yunnan.

47. * *Xenocatantops karnyi* (Kirby, 1910)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

Subtribe *Catantopina* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Catantopsis* Bolivar, 1912

48. *Catantopsis sacalava* Brancsik, 1893

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Africa and Madagascar.

Genus *Diabolocatantops* Jago, 1984

49. *Diabolocatantops innotabilis* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Lakshadweep islands, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Borneo, Cambodia, China, Hong Kong, Indo-China, Japan, Java, Korea, Maldives Islands, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Thailand and Tibet.

50. * *Diabolocatantops pinguis pinguis*
(Stål, 1860)

Distribution: India: Kerala, Manipur, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Cambodia, China, Hainan, Japan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Taiwan.

Genus *Stenocatantops* Dirsh & Uvarov, 1953

51. *Stenocatantops splendens* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution : India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Borneo, China, Celebes, Hainan, Java, Korea, Malaysia, Moluccas Island, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Tribe **Paraconophymatini** Otte, 1995

Genus *Paraconophyma* Uvarov, 1921

52. *Paraconophyma scabra* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Manipur, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Subfamily **COPTACRIDINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Coptacra* Stål, 1873

53. *Coptacra ensifera* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu (Madurai) and Uttarakhand.

54. *Coptacra punctoria* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Coptacrella* Bolivar, 1902

55. *Coptacrella martini* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Epistaurus* Bolivar, 1889

56. *Epistaurus sinetyi* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Manipur, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Eucoptacra* Bolivar, 1902

57. *Eucoptacra ceylonica* Kirby, 1914

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

58. *Eucoptacra praemorsa* (Stål, 1860)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Myanmar, Taiwan and Tenasserim.

Subfamily **CYRTACANTHACRIDINAE** Kirby, 1910

Genus *Chondracris* Uvarov, 1923

59. *Chondracris rosea* (De Geer, 1773)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, Hainan, Indonesia, Japan, Java, Korea, Manchuria, Myanmar, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Tribe **Cyrtacanthacridini** Kirby, 1910

Genus *Anacridium* Uvarov, 1923

60. **Anacridium flavescens* (Fabricius, 1793)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Cyrtacanthacris* Walker, 1870

61. *Cyrtacanthacris tatarica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Bangladesh, Central America, Hainan, Indonesia, Madagascar, Mediterranean Region, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sahara, Saudi Arabia, Seychelles, Sri Lanka, South West Asia, Sumatra and Thailand.

Genus *Patanga* Uvarov, 1923

62. *Patanga japonica* (Bolivar, 1898)

Distribution: India: Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Japan and Pakistan.

63. **Patanga succincta* (Johansson, 1763)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Kerala, Lakshadweep Islands, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Borneo, China, Hainan Island, Japan, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Philippines, Saudi Arabia, Sri Lanka, South East Asia, Sumatra and Taiwan.

Subfamily **EYPREPOCNEMIDINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Tribe **Eyprepocnemidini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Eyprepocnemis* Fieber, 1853

64. **Eyprepocnemis alacris alacris* (Serville, 1838)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Iran, Iraq, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

65. **Eyprepocnemis roseus* Uvarov, 1942

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Punjab and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Tylotropidius* Stål, 1873

66. **Tylotropidius varicornis* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution : India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Heteracris* Walker, 1870

67. *Heteracris pictipes* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

68. *Heteracris pulcher* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **GOMPHOCERINAE** Fieber, 1853

Genus *Brachycrotaphus* Krauss, 1877

69. *Brachycrotaphus indicus* Uvarov, 1932

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

70. *Brachycrotaphus longiceps* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Dhimbana* Henry, 1940

71. *Dhimbana dawsoni* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka (Bliligirirangan Hills) and Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district; Erode district: Dhimbam).

Genus *Gelastorhinus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

72. *Gelastorhinus semipictus* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

73. *Gelastorhinus tryxaloides* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai and Kodaikanal).

Genus *Leva* Bolivar, 1909

74. *Leva indica* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Madurea* Bolivar, 1902

75. *Madurea cephalotes* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai).

Genus *Phonogaster* Henry, 1940

76. *Phonogaster cariniventris* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Karnataka (Bliligirirangan Hills), Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district; Erode district: Dhimbam) and Tripura.

Tribe **Ochrilidini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Gonista* Bolivar, 1898

77. *Gonista sagitta* (Uvarov, 1912)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Manipur, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Myanmar, Northern Iran and Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Arcypterini** Shumakov, 1963

Genus *Aulacobothrus* Bolivar, 1902

78. *Aulacobothrus luteipes infernus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka,

Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Japan, Europe, Myanmar, North America, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

79. **Aulacothrus luteipes luteipes* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Europe, Japan, Myanmar, Nepal, North America, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Taiwan and Thailand.

80. *Aulacothrus socius* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Odisha and Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal district: Perumalmalai).

81. *Aulacothrus strictus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Madhya Pradesh and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

82. *Aulacothrus taeniatus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Europe, Japan, Myanmar and North Africa.

Genus *Crucinotacris* Jago, 1996

83. *Crucinotacris decisa* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Europe, Japan, Myanmar, North America and Pakistan.

Genus *Leionotacris* Jago, 1996

84. *Leionotacris bolivari* Uvarov, 1921

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: East Africa and East Afghanistan.

Subfamily **HEMIACRIDINAE** Dirsh, 1956

Genus *Calamippa* Henry, 1940

85. *Calamippa prasina* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Genus *Clonacris* Uvarov, 1943

86. *Clonacris kirbyi* (Finot, 1903)

Distribution: India: Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

87. *Clonacris sila* Rehn, 1944

Distribution: India: Bihar and Tamil Nadu.

Tribe **Hieroglyphini** Bolívar, 1912

Genus *Hieroglyphus* Krauss, 1877

88. *Hieroglyphus banian* (Fabricius, 1978)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh and Pakistan.

89. **Hieroglyphus oryzivorus* Carl, 1916

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh and Pakistan.

Tribe **Laptacriini** Johnston, 1956

Genus *Laptacris* Walker, 1870

90. *Laptacris filiformis* Walker, 1870

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **OEDIPODINAE** Walker, 1871

Genus *Morphacris* Walker, 1870

91. *Morphacris fasciata* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Portugal, South Africa, Spain, Sudan, Turkey and Yemen.

Tribe **Acrotylini** Shumakov, 1963

Genus *Acrotylus* Fieber, 1853

92. **Acrotylus humberianus* Saussure, 1884

Distribution: India: Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

93. *Acrotylus insubricus insubricus* (Scopoli, 1786)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Goa, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Algeria, Bulgaria, Egypt, France, Gambia, Iran, Italy, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Spain, Turkey and Yemen.

Genus *Chloebora* Saussure, 1884

94. *Chloebora crassa* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

95. *Chloebora grossa* Saussure, 1884

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

96. *Chloebora marshalli* (Henry, 1933)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Dittopternis* Saussure, 1884

97. **Dittopternis venusta* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

98. *Dittopternis zebrata* Saussure, 1884

Distribution: India: Eastern India and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Myanmar.

Tribe **Parapleurini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

99. *Ceracris nigricornis nigricornis* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Myanmar, South China, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Tribe **Epacromiini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Aiolopus* Fieber, 1853

100. **Aiolopus simulatrix simulatrix* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Islands of Indian Ocean, Pakistan, Myanmar, Seychelles and Westwards.

101. **Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus* (Fabricius, 1798)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Bangladesh, Borneo, Brunei, Celebes, China, Hainan, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Japan, Java, Lombok, Malaysia, Myanmar, New Guinea, Pakistan, Papua, Philippines, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Timor.

Tribe **Locustini** Kirby, 1825

Genus *Gastrimargus* Saussure, 1884

102. *Gastrimargus africanus africanus* (Saussure, 1888)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Tibet and Yemen.

103. **Gastrimargus marmoratus* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Borneo, Celebes, China, Hong Kong, Japan, Java, Korea, Lombok, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Philippines, Sulawesi, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Genus *Oedaleus* Fieber, 1853

104. **Oedaleus abruptus* Thunberg, 1815

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Pudhucherry, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, China, Indo-China, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

105. *Oedaleus nigrofasciatus* (Saussure, 1773)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Italy and South Africa.

106. **Oedaleus senegalensis* (Krauss, 1877)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, North Africa, Pakistan and Western USSR.

Genus *Pternoscirta* Saussure, 1884

107. *Pternoscirta bimaculata* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

108. *Pternoscirta caliginiosa* (De Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

109. *Pternoscirta cinctifemur* (Walker, 1859)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Goa, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Eastern Nepal and Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Epacromiini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Heteropternis* Stål, 1873

Species *respondens* (Walker, 1859)

110. Subspecies *Heteropternis respondens respondens* (Walker, 1859)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Indonesia, Japan, Java, Malacca, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Taiwan.

111. *Heteropternis thoracica* (Walker, 1870)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Hilethera* Uvarov, 1923

112. *Hilethera oedipodioides* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Sphingonotini** Johnston, 1956

Genus *Sphingonotus* Fieber, 1852

113. *Sphingonotus (Sphingonotus) longipennis* Saussure, 1884

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Manipur, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Africa, Bangladesh, Europe, Mongolia, Northeast Nepal and Southeast Tibet.

114. *Sphingonotus (Sphingonotus) savignyi savignyi* Saussure, 1884

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Africa, Egypt and North Africa.

Tribe **Trilophidiini** Shumakov, 1963

Genus *Trilophidia* Stål, 1873

115. **Trilophidia annulata* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Borneo, China, Hong Kong, Japan, Java, Korea, Malaysia, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sarawak, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Subfamily **OXYINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Chitaura* Bolivar, 1918

116. *Chitaura indica* Uvarov, 1929

Distribution: India: Karnataka (Mysuru Plateau, Coorg, Sidapuru), Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Gesonula* Uvarov, 1940

117. **Gesonula punctifrons* (Stål, 1861)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Borneo, China, Hainan, Japan, Java, Kalimantan, Malacca, Myanmar, North Vietnam, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand and Tongking.

Tribe **Oxyini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Oxya* Serville, 1831

118. **Oxya fuscovittata* (Marschall, 1836)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland,

Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan and USSR.

119. **Oxya hyla hyla* Serville, 1831

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Africa, Angola, Bangladesh, Benin, Cameroun, Chad, Central African Republic, Cote d'Ivoire, Fernandopo, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Iran, Kenya, Liberia, Madagascar, Maldives Islands, Mali, Malawi, Nepal, Niger, Nigeria, Pakistan, Sao Thome, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Sri Lanka, Tanzania, Uganda, Zaire and Zambia.

120. **Oxya japonica japonica* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Andaman islands, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Australia, China, Pakistan, Singapore and Sri Lanka.

121. **Oxya nitidula* (Walker, 1971)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

122. **Oxya velox* (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Myanmar, Pakistan, Singapore, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

Subfamily SPATHOSTERNINAE Rehn, 1957

Tribe **Spathosternini** Rehn, 1957

Genus *Spathosternum* Krauss, 1877

123. **Spathosternum prasiniferum prasiniferum* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh,

Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Hainan, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, South and East China, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Vietnam and West Malaysia.

124. **Spathosternum venulosum* Stål, 1878

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **TERATIDINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Tribe **Teratodini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Teratodes* Brulle, 1835

125. *Teratodes brachypterus* Carl, 1916

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

126. *Teratodes monticollis* (Gray, 1832)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **TROPIDOPOLINAE** Jacobson, 1945

Tribe **Tristriini** Mishchenko, 1945

Genus *Tristria* Stål, 1873

127. **Tristria pulvinata* (Uvarov, 1921)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Haryana, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Superfamily **EUMASTACOIDEA**

Family **MASTACIDEIDAE**

Subfamily **MASTACIDEINAE**

Genus *Mastacides* Bolivar, 1899

128. *Mastacides crassipes* Bolivar, 1930

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Palani Hills).

129. *Mastacides nilgiriscus* Bolivar, 1914

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri Hills: Ootacamund).

130. *Mastacides pterolepis* Burr, 1889

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai and Kodaikanal districts).

131. *Mastacides pupaeformis* Burr, 1889

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal district).

Genus *Paramastacides* Descamps, 1974

132. *Paramastacides gracilipes* (Bolivar, 1930)

Distribution: India: Karnataka (Shimoga: Sagar Taluk) and Tamil Nadu.

133. *Paramastacides ramachandrai* (Bolivar, 1930)

Distribution: India: Karnataka (Siddapur) and Tamil Nadu.

134. *Paramastacides stuartensis* (Bolivar, 1930)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district).

Superfamily **PYRGOMORPHOIDEA** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Family **PYRGOMORPHIDAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Subfamily **ORTHACRIDINAE** Bolívar, 1905

Tribe **Orthacridini** Bolívar, 1905

Genus group *Orthacris*

Genus *Neorthacris* Kevan & Singh, 1964

Species *acuticeps* (Bolívar, 1902)

135.

Subspecies **Neorthacris acuticeps acuticeps* (Bolívar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district: Pollachi; Madurai district).

136. *Neorthacris acuticeps nilgiriensis* (Uvarov, 1929)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri Hills).

137. *Neorthacris longicerata* Singh & Kevan, 1965

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

138. *Neorthacris malabarensis* Singh & Kevan, 1965

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

139. *Neorthacris palnensis* (Uvarov, 1929)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Palani Hills: Thandikudi, Upper Palani Hills, Vandaravu).

140. **Neorthacris simulans* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Genus *Orthacris* Bolívar, 1884

Subgenus *Orthacris* Bolívar, 1884

141. *Orthacris (Orthacris) ceylonica* (Kirby, 1914)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

142. *Orthacris (Orthacris) comorensis* Singh & Kevan, 1965

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

143. *Orthacris (Orthacris)*

maindroni Bolívar, 1905

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subgenus *Pseudorthacris* Kevan & Singh, 1964

144. *Orthacris (Pseudorthacris)*

elegans Bolívar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

145. *Orthacris (Pseudorthacris) incongruens* Carl, 1916

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

146. *Orthacris (Pseudorthacris) ramakrishnai* Bolivar, 1918

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

147. *Orthacris (Pseudorthacris) robusta* Kevan, 1935

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

148. *Orthacris (Pseudorthacris) ruficornis* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Tribe **Popoviini** Kevan & Akbar, 1964

Genus *Colemania* Bolívar, 1910

149. **Colemania sphenarioides* Bolívar, 1910

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Nigiracris* Kevan, 1964

150. *Nigiracris raoi* (Kevan, 1952)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **PYRGOMORPHINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Tribe **Atractomorphini** Bolívar, 1905

151. **Atractomorpha crenulata crenulata* (Fabricius, 1793)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Lakshadweep Islands, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Cambodia, Laos, Maldives Islands, Malaya, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, South Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Thailand.

Tribe **Chrotogonini** Bolívar, 1904

Genus *Chrotogonus* Serville, 1838

Subgenus *Chrotogonus* Serville, 1838

152.

**Chrotogonus (Chrotogonus) brachypterus*

Bolivar, 1904

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

153.

**Chrotogonus (Chrotogonus) oxypterus* (Blanchard, 1836)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh and Sri Lanka.

154.

**Chrotogonus (Chrotogonus) trachypterus trachypterus* (Blanchard, 1836)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Iran, Nepal and Pakistan.

Tribe **Monistriini** Kevan & Akbar, 1964

Genus *Pileolum* Bolivar, 1918

155. *Pileolum kirbyi* Bolivar, 1914

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri Hills: Ootacamund).

Tribe **Poekilocerini** Burmeister, 1840

Genus *Poekilocerus* Serville, 1831

156. **Poekilocerus pictus* (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Nepal and Pakistan.

Tribe **Pyrgomorphini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1874

Sub tribe **Pyrgomorphina** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1874

Genus *Anarchita* Bolivar, 1904

157. *Anarchita aptera* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Plerisca* Bolivar, 1904

158. *Plerisca sudinica* Schmidt, 2004

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Pyrgomorpha* Serville, 1838

159. *Pyrgomorpha bispinosa bispinosa* Walker, 1870

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Zarytes* Bolivar, 1904

160. *Zarytes squalinus brachycerus* (Kirby, 1914)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

161. *Zarytes squalinus squalinus* (Saussure, 1884)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Tribe **Taphronotini** Bolivar, 1904

Subtribe **Aularchina** Kevan & Akbar, 1964

Genus *Aularches* Stål, 1873

162. *Aularches miliaris miliaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Cambodia, Indonesia, Java, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Tibet, South Vietnam and West Malaysia.

Superfamily **TETRIGOIDEA** Serville, 1838

Family **TETRIGIDAE** Serville, 1838

Subfamily **CLADONOTINAE** Bolivar, 1887

Genus *Deltonotus* Hancock, 1904

163. *Deltonotus gibbiceps* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

164. *Deltonotus humilis* Hebard, 1929

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Epitettix* Hancock, 1907

165. *Epitettix tamilus* Gunther, 1939

Distribution: India: Kerala, Mizoram and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Hancockella* Uvarov, 1940

166. *Hancockella portentosa* (Kirby, 1914)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Tettlobus* Hancock, 1909

167. *Tettlobus prashdi* Gunther, 1938

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **DISCOTETTIGINAE** Hancock, 1907

Genus *Indoniriatra* Tinkham, 1939

168. *Indoniriatra provertex* (Hancock, 1912)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Mazarredia* Bolivar, 1887

169. *Mazarredia (Mazarredia) cristulata* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **SCELIMENINAE**

Tribe **Thoradontini** Kevan, 1966

Genus *Bolivaritettix* Gunther, 1939

170. *Bolivaritettix javanicus* (Bolivar, 1909)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Fuji, Java, Malaysia and Nepal.

171. *Bolivaritettix nathani* Wagan & Kevan, 1992

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Eucriotettix* Hebard, 1929

172. *Eucriotettix exsertus* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

173. *Eucriotettix flavopictus* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Myanmar.

174. *Eucriotettix oculatus* Bolivar, 1898

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Java, Hainan, South China and Sumatra.

175. *Eucriotettix spinilobus* Hancock, 1904

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Pinang and Sri Lanka.

176. * *Eucriotettix tricarinatus* (Bolivar, 1887)

Distribution: India: Kerala, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka and Sumba.

177. *Thoradonta apiculata* Hancock, 1915

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka and Sumba.

178. *Thoradonta nodulosa* (Stål, 1860)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh,

Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Borneo, China, Hainan, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar, Perak, Pinang, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Sumba and Sumatra.

Genus *Xistrella* Bolivar, 1909

179. *Xistrella stylata* (Hancock, 1907)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Tribe **Criotettigini** Kevan, 1966

Genus *Criotettix* Bolivar, 1877

180. **Criotettix bispinosus* (Dalman, 1818)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, England, Germany and Sri Lanka.

181. *Criotettix indicus* Bolivar, 1902

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

182. *Criotettix orientalis* Hancock, 1913

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Tribe **Scelimenini** Hancock, 1907

Genus *Euscelimena* Gunther, 1938

183. **Euscelimena harpago* (Serville, 1839)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Karnataka, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

184. **Scelimena product producta* (Serville, 1838)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Java, Malaysia, Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Gavialidium* Saussure, 1861

185. *Gavialidium carli* Hebard, 1929

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **TETRIGINAE**

Genus *Ergatettix* Kirby, 1914

186. **Ergatettix dorsiferus* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, China, Central Asia, Greater Sunda Islands, Iran, Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan and Turkmenistan.

187. * *Ergatettix interruptus* (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Carin Cheba, China, Myanmar, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Hedotettix* Bolivar, 1887

188. * *Hedotettix gracilis* (De Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Celebes, China, Java, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Sulawesi, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Tribe *Dinotettigini* Gunther, 1979

Genus *Lamellitettix* Hancock, 1904

189. *Lamellitettix fletcheri* Hancock, 1905

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Philippines and Sri Lanka.

Tribe *Tetrigini* Serville, 1838

Genus *Copotettix* Bolivar, 1887

190. *Copotettix indicus* Hancock, 1912

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Genus *Euparatettix* Hancock, 1904

191. *Euparatettix histricus* Stål, 1861

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Borneo, Caledonia, Celebes, East Africa, East Afghanistan, Holland, Indonesia, Iran, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Ireland, Pakistan, Philippines, Queensland, Saudi Arabia, Solomon Islands, South China, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Taiwan.

192. **Euparatettix indicus* Bolivar, 1887

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: china and East Indies.

193. *Euparatettix variabilis* (Bolivar, 1887)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Britain, Borneo, Java, Myanmar, New Guinea, Pakistan, Papua, Philippines, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Taiwan.

Genus *Paratettix* Bolivar, 1887

194. *Paratettix cingalensis* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Tripura.

Elsewhere: Borneo, Hainan, Java, Malaysia, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Taiwan.

195. *Paratettix hirsutus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Distribution: India: Assam, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and Tripura.

Elsewhere: Myanmar.

196. **Paratettix scaber* Thunberg, 1815

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Africa.

Genus *Tetrix* Latreille, 1802

197. *Tetrix bipunctatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: India: Manipur, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: China, Europe, North and West asia, North America and Russia.

Subfamily **METRODORINAE** Bolivar, 1887

Genus *Systolederus* Bolivar, 1887

198. *Systolederus greeni* Bolivar, 1892

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Infrorder **TRIDACTYLIDEA**

Superfamily **TRYDACTYLOIDEA** Brulle, 1835

Family **TRIDACTYLIDAE** Brulle, 1835

Subfamily **TRIDACTYLINAE** Brulle, 1835

Genus *Xya* Latreille, 1809

199. *Xya castetsi* (Bolivar, 1902)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

200. *Xya curta* (Chopard, 1936)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

201. *Xya riparia* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Sudorder **ENSIFERA**

Infrorder **OEDISCHIDEA**

Superfamily **GRYLLOIDEA**

Family **GRYLLIDAE**

Subfamily **GRYLLINAE** Laicharding, 1781

Genus *Acanthoplistis* Saussure, 1877

202. *Acanthoplistis birmanus* Saussure, 1877

Distribution: India: Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Annam, Myanmar, Thailand and Tonkin.

Genus *Callogryllus* Sjoestedt, 1909

203. *Callogryllus bilineatus* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

204. *Callogryllus curtipennis* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

205. *Callogryllus gravelyi* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

206. *Callogryllus orientalis* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

207. *Callogryllus subopacus* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Grylloderes* Bolivar, 1894

208. *Grylloderes brunneri* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa and Bangladesh.

209. *Grylloderes melanocephalus* (Serville, 1839)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Myanmar and Nepal.

Genus *Gryllus* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus *Gryllus* Linnaeus, 1758

210. *Gryllus (Gryllus) bimaculatus* De Geer, 1773

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh,

Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Puducherry, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Malaysia, Mediterranean Region, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Singapore and Sri Lanka.

211. *Gryllus (Gryllus) quadrimaculatus* Saussure, 1877

Distribution: India: Assam, Karnataka, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Annam.

Genus *Gymnogryllus* Saussure, 1877

212. *Gymnogryllus kashmirensis* Bhowmik, 1967

Distribution: India: Assam, Bihar, Goa, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Puducherry, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Indonesia, Myanmar and South Vietnam.

Genus *Itaropsis* Chopard, 1925

213. *Itaropsis tenella* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Goa, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Malaysia and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Loxoblemmus* Saussure, 1877

214. *Loxoblemmus cavifrons* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Puducherry and Tamil Nadu.

215. *Loxoblemmus equestris* Saussure, 1877

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Celebes, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Mitius* Gorochof, 1985

216. *Mitius blennus* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Assam, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Solomon Islands and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Phonarellus* Gorochov, 1983

217. *Phonarellus (Phonarellus) erythrocephalus erythrocephalus* (Serville, 1839)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

218. *Phonarellus (Phonarellus) humeralis* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Tonkin and Vietnam.

219. *Phonarellus (Phonarellus) minor* (Chopard, 1959)

Distribution: India: Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Iran, Java, Myanmar, Pakistan and South Vietnam.

Genus *Plebeiogryllus* Randell, 1964

220. *Plebeiogryllus guttiventris guttiventris* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Puducherry, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Scapsipedoides* Chopard, 1936

221. *Scapsipedoides macrocephalus* Chopard, 1936

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Tarbinskiellus* Gorochov, 1983

222. *Tarbinskiellus orientalis* (Burmeister, 1838)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Malaysia, Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

223. *Tarbinskiellus portentosus* (Lichtenstein, 1796)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya,

Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Indonesia, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore and Taiwan.

224. *Tarbinskiellus terrificus* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. Genus *Teleogryllus* Chopard, 1961

225. *Teleogryllus flavovittatus* (Chopard, 1928)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

226. *Teleogryllus triangulifer* (Chopard, 1969)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu.

Subgenus *Brchyteleogryllus* Gorochov, 1988

227. *Teleogryllus (Brchyteleogryllus) occipitalis* (Serville, 1838)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Lakshadweep, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Annam, Bangladesh, Bangkok, Bhutan, Borneo, Celebes, China, Indonesia, Indo-China, Japan, Java, Kuala Lumpur, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, Sarawak, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Sulawesi, Taiwan, Thailand, Tibet and Vietnam.

Subgenus *Macroteleogryllus* Gorochov, 1988

228. *Teleogryllus (Macroteleogryllus) mitratus* (Burmeister, 1838)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Puducherry, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Annam, Bangkok, Borneo, China, Indonesia, Indo-China, Japan, Java, Johore, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, Pinang, Sarawak, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan, Tenasserin, Thailand and Vietnam.

Genus *Coiblemmus* Chopard, 1936

229. *Coiblemmus compactus* (Chopard, 1928)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Velarifictorus* Randell, 1964

Subgenus *Velarifictorus* Randell, 1964

230. *Velarifictorus (Velarifictorus) asperses* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Annam, Borneo, China, Java, Hong Kong, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Selangor, Singapore, Sri Lanka and Taiwan.

231. *Velarifictorus (Velarifictorus) fallax* (Chopard, 1969)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

232. *Velarifictorus (Velarifictorus) maindroni* (Chopard, 1969)

Distribution: India: Chandigarh and Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Cunnoor).

Tribe **Cophogryllini** Ichikawa, Murai & Honda, 2000

Genus *Cophogryllus* Saussure, 1877

233. *Cophogryllus brevipes* Chopard, 1933

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Udthagamandalam).

234. *Cophogryllus carli* Chopard, 1933

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Palani Hills: Thandikudi).

Tribe **Modicogryllini** Otte & Alexander, 1983

Genus *Apteroeryncus* Gorochof, 1990

235. *Apteroeryncus martini* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Grylloides* Saussure, 1874

236. * *Grylloides sigillatus* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Malacca, Malaysia, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Gryllopsis* Chopard, 1928

237. *Gryllopsis arenicola* (Annandale, 1906)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai and Ramanathapuram districts).

238. *Gryllopsis femorata* Chopard, 1935

Distribution: India: Chandigarh, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya and Tamil Nadu (Selam district).

239. *Gryllopsis furcata* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: China and Myanmar.

240. *Gryllopsis robusta* Chopard, 1933

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Chengalpattu district).

Genus *Modicogryllus* Chopard, 1961

Subgenus *Modicogryllus* Chopard, 1961

241. *Modicogryllus (Modicogryllus) confirmatus* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Indo-China, Iran, Israel, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

242. *Modicogryllus (Modicogryllus) facialis* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

Subgenus *Promodicogryllus* Gorochof, 1986

243. *Modicogryllus (Promodicogryllus) ehsani* Chopard, 1961

Distribution: India: Assam, Chandigarh, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

Tribe **Turanogryllini** Otte, 1987

Genus *Turanogryllus* *Tarbinskii*, 1940

244. *Turanogryllus histrio* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bhutan and Nepal.

245. *Turanogryllus jammuensis* (Bhowmik, 1976)

Distribution: India: Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

246. *Turanogryllus maculithorax* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

247. *Turanogryllus virgulatus* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

Subfamily **LANDREVINAE** Gorochoy, 1882

Tribe **Landrevini** Gorochoy, 1982

Genus ***Landreva*** Walker, 1869

248. *Landreva hemiptera* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

249. *Landreva semialata* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **SCLEROGRYLLINAE** Gorochoy, 1985

Tribe **Sclerogryllini** Gorochoy, 1985

Genus ***Sclerogryllus*** Gorochoy, 1985

250. *Sclerogryllus coreaceus* (Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Annam, China, Indonesia, Japan, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar, Sarawak, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand and Vietnam.

Subfamily **CACHOPLISTINAE** Saussure, 1877

Tribe **Homogryllini** Gorochoy, 1986

Genus ***Melimorpha*** Walker, 1870

251. *Melimorpha cincticornis* Walker, 1870

Distribution: India: Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Pakistan.

Subfamily **PHALANGOPSINAE** Blanchard, 1845

Genus ***Kempiola*** Uvarov, 1940

252. *Kempiola maindroni* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Tribe **Heterogryllini** Hebard, 1928

Genus ***Arachomimus*** Saussure, 1878

Subgenus ***Arachomimus*** Saussure, 1897

253. *Arachomimus (Arachomimus) anullicornis* Chopard, 1936

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

254. *Arachomimus (Arachomimus) Lepidus* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Selam district: Shervarayan Hills).

Genus ***Aspidogryllus*** Chopard, 1933

255. *Aspidogryllus singularis* Chopard, 1933

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Udthagamandalam).

Genus ***Phalangopsina*** Chopard, 1933

256. *Phalangopsina bolivari* Desutter-Grandcolas, 2012

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

257. *Phalangopsina Chopardi* Desutter-Grandcolas, 2012

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

258. *Phalangopsina dubia* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

259. *Phalangopsina graveleyi* Desutter-Grandcolas, 2012

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Udthagamandalam).

260. *Phalangopsina palpata* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Subfamily **PODOSCIPTINAE**

Genus ***Corixogryllus*** Bolivar, 1900

261. *Corixogryllus abbreviatus* Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

Genus ***Mnesibulus*** Stål, 1877

262. *Mnesibulus (Mnesibulus) andrewesi* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district).

Genus ***Prozvenella*** Gorochoy, 2002

263. *Prozvenella saussureana* (Guerin, 1844)

Distribution: India: Pudhucherry, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

264. *Prozvenella similis meridionalis* Gorochoy, 2002

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district).

Genus ***Varitrella*** Gorochoy, 2003

265. *Varitrella (Varitrella) varipennis* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **NEMOBIINAE**

Tribe **Pteronemobiini** Otte & Alexander, 1983

Genus *Dianemobius* Vickery, 1973

266. *Dianemobius csikii* (Bolivar, 1901)

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Bhutan, China, Myanmar, Siberia and Sri Lanka.

267. *Dianemobius fascipes* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Sri Lanka and Taiwan.

Genus *Polionemobius* Gorochov, 1983

268. *Polionemobius taprobanensis* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, China, Indonesia, Malacca, Malaysia, Myanmar, Perak, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Vietnam.

Genus *Pteronemobius* Jacobson and Bianchi, 1905

Subgenus *Pteronemobius* Jacobson, 1904

269. *Pteronemobius (Pteronemobius) heydeni concolor* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Malaysia, Myanmar, Perak, Sri Lanka and Turkistan.

270. *Pteronemobius (Pteronemobius) indicus* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Goa, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Indo-China, Malaysia, Mentawi Islands, Myanmar, Pinang, Sri Lanka, Sumatra, Taiwan and Thailand.

271. *Pteronemobius (Pteronemobius)*

pantelchopardum Shishodia & Varshney, 1987

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

Genus *Stenonemobius* Gorochov, 1981

Subgenus *Ocellonemobius* Gorochov, 1981

272. *Stenonemobius (Ocellonemobius) bicolor bicolor* (Saussure, 1877)

Distribution: India: Bihar, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

Tribe **Nemobiini** Saussure, 1877

Genus *Paranemobius* Saussure, 1877

273. *Paranemobius pictus* Saussure, 1877

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **OECANTHINAE** Blanchard, 1845

Tribe **Oecanthini** Blanchard, 1845

Genus *Oecanthus* Serville, 1831

274. *Oecanthus bilineatus* Chopard, 1937

Distribution: India: Odisha, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Nepal.

275. *Oecanthus henryi* Chopard, 1936

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

276. **Oecanthus indicus* Saussure, 1878

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Amboine, China, Japan, Malaysia, Malaya Archipelago, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Pinang, Sri Lanka, Sumba and Vietnam.

277. *Oecanthus rufescence* Serville, 1839

Distribution: India: Maharashtra, Punjab, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Celebes, Fiji, Malaysia, Sri Lanka and Timor.

Subfamily **PTEROPLISTINAE** Chopard, 1936
Tribe **Pteroplistini** Chopard, 1936

Genus *Pteroplistes* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1873

278. *Pteroplistes platycleis* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

Subfamily **ITARINAE** Chopard, 1932

Tribe **Itarini** Chopard, 1932

Genus *Itara* Walker, 1869

Subgenus *Phormincter* Saussure, 1878

279. *Itara (Phormincter) microcephala* (Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Borneo, Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore and Sumatra.

Subfamily **EUSCYRTINAE** Otte, 1994

Genus *Euscyrtes* Guerin-Meneville, 1844

Subgenus *Osus* Gorochof, 1987

280. *Euscyrtes (Osus) concinnus* (Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Java, Malaysia, Moluccas, Myanmar, North Australia, Philippines, Selanjor, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Tropical Asia and Thailand.

281. *Euscyrtes (Osus) hemelytrus* (Haan, 1842)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Assam, Jammu & Kashmir, Kerala, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Batavia, China, Japan, Java, Kuala Lumpur, Korea, Malaysia, Moluccas, Myanmar, North America, Philippines, Sri Lanka and Taiwan.

Genus *Patiscus* Stål, 1877

282. *Patiscus quadripunctatus* Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Family **TRIGINIDIIDAE** Saussure, 1874

Tribe **Trigonidiini** Saussure, 1874

Genus *Amusurgus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Subgenus *Amusurgus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

283. *Amusurgus (Amusurgus) fulvus* Chopard, 1969

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Malaysia, Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Sumatra.

284. *Amusurgus (Amusurgus) oedemeroides* (Walker, 1871)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

285. *Amusurgus (Amusurgus) unicolor* Chopard, 1925

Distribution: India: Chandigarh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka and Sumatra.

Genus *Anaxipha* Saussure, 1874

286. * *Anaxipha longipennis* (Serville, 1839)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Australia, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mauritius, Myanmar, Philippines, Queensland, Seychelles, Sri Lanka and Tropical Asia.

287. *Anaxipha nigrithorax* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Eppukadu).

Genus *Homoeoxipha* Saussure, 1874

288. *Homoeoxipha lycoides* (Walker, 1896)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Lakshadweep Islands, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Bangladesh, China, Malaysia, Maldives Islands, Myanmar, Nepal, Perak, Queensland, Singapore, Sri Lanka and Taiwan.

Genus *Metioche* Stål, 1877

Subgenus *Metioche* Stål, 1877

289. * *Metioche (Metioche) bicolor* (Stål, 1861)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: China, Java and Malaysia.

290. *Metioche (Metioche) gigas* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

291. *Metioche (Metioche) pallidinervis*

Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

292. * *Metioche (Metioche) vittacollis vittacollis* (Stål, 1861)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Assam and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Malaysia and Philippines.

Genus *Metiochodes* Chopard, 1931

293. *Metiochodes greeni* (Chopard, 1925)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Trigonidium* Rambur, 1838

294. *Trigonidium humbertianum* (Saussure, 1878)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Iran, Malaysia and Sri Lanka.

Subgenus *Trigonidium* Rambur, 1839

295. *Trigonidium (Trigonidium) cicindeloides* Rambur, 1839

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Lakshadweep Islands, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Bhutan, China, Japan, Korea, Madagascar, Malaysia, Maldives Islands, Mauritius, Mediterranean Regions, Myanmar, Nepal, South Europe, Sri Lanka and Vietnam.

Family **GRYLLOTALPIDAE** Blanchard, 1845
Subfamily **GRYLLOTALPINAE** Blanchard, 1845

Genus *Gryllotalpa* Latreille, 1802

296. **Gryllotalpa africana* Beauvois, 1805

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal

Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Odisha, Pudhucherry, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Burma, Iran, Madagascar, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Singapore, Sri Lanka and South Spain.

Subfamily **SCAPTERISCINAE** Zeuner, 1939

Genus *Indioscapter* Nickle, 2003

297. *Indioscapter leptodactylus* Chopard, 1928

Distribution: India: Assam, Jharkhand, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh.

Family **MOGOPLISTIDAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1873

Subfamily **MOGOPLISTINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1873

Tribe **Mogoplistini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1873

Genus *Derectaotus* Chopard, 1936

298. *Derectaotus maindroni* (Chopard, 1928)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Cunnor), Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh.

Genus *Ornebius* Guerin, 1844

299. *Ornebius guerini* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

300. *Ornebius nigripalpis* Guerin, 1844

Distribution: India: Pudhucherry, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Superfamily **STENOPELMATOIDEA**

Burmeister, 1838

Family **ANOSTOSTOMATIDAE** Saussure, 1859

Subfamily **ANOSTOSTOMATINAE** Saussure, 1859

Genus *Hypocophoides* Karny, 1930

301. *Hypocophoides biforaminiatus* Griffini, 1914

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

302. *Hypocophoides indicus* (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Family **GRYLLACRIDIDAE** Blanchard, 1845
Subfamily **GRYLLACRIDINAE** Blanchard, 1845

Genus *Brachyntheisogryllacris* Karny, 1937

303. *Brachyntheisogryllacris abbreviata evolutior* (Griffini, 1909)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

304. *Brachyntheisogryllacris bertrandi*

(Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).**305. *Brachyntheisogryllacris buyssoniana kurseonga*** Griffini, 1913**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.**306. *Brachyntheisogryllacris maindroni*** (Griffini, 1913)**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Cunnor).Genus *Capnogryllacris* Karny, 1937**307. *Capnogryllacris fumigata*** (Haan, 1842)**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu**Elsewhere:** Borneo, Java, Malaya and Sumatra.Genus *Diaphanogryllacris* Karny, 1937**308. *Diaphanogryllacris gladiator*** (Fabricius, 1793)**Distribution:** India: Kerala, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.Genus *Eremus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1888**309. *Eremus decolyi*** Bolivar, 1900**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).**310. *Eremus elongatulus*** Bolivar, 1900**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal: Shenbaganur).Genus *Eugryllacris* Karny, 1937**311. *Eugryllacris panteli*** (Bolivar, 1900)**Distribution:** India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).Genus *Gryllacris* Serville, 1831**312. *Gryllacris barnesi*** Chopard, 1937**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Naduvattam).Genus *Hapogryllacris* Karny, 1937**313. *Hapogryllacris simplex*** (Walker, 1871)**Distribution:** India: Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.**Elsewhere:** Sri Lanka.Genus *Melaneremus* Karny, 1937**314. *Melaneremus papulus*** (Bolivar, 1900)**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).Genus *Neanias* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1888**315. *Neanias atroterminatus*** Karny, 1937**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district).Genus *Niphetogryllacris* Karny, 1937**316. *Niphetogryllacris succinea*** (Bolivar, 1900)**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Dindukkal district: Kodaikanal).Genus *Phryganogryllacris* Karny, 1937**317. *Phryganogryllacris nivea*** (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1888)**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).Family **STENOPELMATIDAE** Burmeister, 1838Subfamily **ORYCTOPINAE** Kevan, 1986Genus *Oryctopus* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1888**318. *Oryctopus bolivari*** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1888**Distribution:** India: Pudhucherry and Tamil Nadu.**319. *Oryctopus prodigiosus*** Bolivar, 1900**Distribution:** India: Tamil Nadu (Thiruchirappalli district).Superfamily **TETTIGONIOIDEA** Krauss, 1910Family **TETTIGONIDAE** Krauss, 1902Subfamily **CONOCEPHALINAE** Burmeister, 1838Tribe **Conocephalini** Burmeister, 1838Genus *Conocephalus* Thunberg, 1815Subgenus *Amurocephalus* Storozhenko, 2004**320. *Conocephalus (Amurocephalus) chinensis*** (Redtenbacher, 1891)**Distribution:** India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.**Elsewhere:** Amur, China, Korea and Russia.Subgenus *Anisoptera* Latreille, 1829**321. *Conocephalus (Anisoptera) honorei*** (Bolivar, 1900)**Distribution:** India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).**322. **Conocephalus (Anisoptera) longipennis*** (Haan, 1842)**Distribution:** India: Assam and Tamil Nadu.**Elsewhere:** Caroline Islands, Java, Malaysia, Philippines, Ponapean Island, Singapore and Sumatra.**323. **Conocephalus (Anisoptera) maculatus*** (Le Gouilou, 1841)**Distribution:** India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Africa, Australia, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Java, Malaysia, Nepal, New Guinea, Philippines and Sierra Leone.

Tribe **Copiphorini** Karny, 1912

Genus *Euconocephalus* Karny, 1907

324. *Euconocephalus incertus (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Pudhucherry, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Borneo, China, Java, Myanmar, Pinang, Sri Lanka and Sumatra.

325. *Euconocephalus indicus (Redtenbacher, 1891)

Distribution: India: Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Australia, Java and Malaysia.

326. Euconocephalus pallidus (Redtenbacher, 1891)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Gujarat, Kerala, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bangladesh, Borneo, East Indies, Java, Myanmar, Philippines, Pinang, Singapore, Sri Lanka and Tonkin.

Genus *Gonatacanthus* Karny, 1907

327. Gonatacanthus primitivus Ingrisch, 1998

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Nilagiri district: Devala).

328. Gonatacanthus pulcher (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).

Genus *Pseudacrodonta* Ingrisch, 1998

329. Pseudacrodonta nigrospinosa (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Subtribe **Oxylakina** Ingrisch, 1998

Genus *Oxylakis* Redtenbacher, 1891

330. Oxylakis punctipennis Redtenbacher, 1891

Distribution: India: Delhi and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Borneo.

331. Oxylakis truncatipennis Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Subfamily **HEXACENTRINAE** Karny, 1925

Genus *Euhexacentrus* Hebard, 1922

332. Euhexacentrus annulicornis (Stål, 1877)

Distribution: India: Assam, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Aru Islands, China, Japan, Moluccas and Philippines.

Genus *Hexacentrus* Serville, 1831

333. Hexacentrus major Redtenbacher, 1891

Distribution: India: Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

334. Hexacentrus unicolor Serville, 1831

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Himachal Pradesh, Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Borneo, Celebes, China, Japan, Java, Moluccas, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Sumatra, Taiwan and Thailand.

Subfamily **LISTROSCOLIDINAE**

Redtenbacher, 1891

Tribe **Phisidini** Jin, Xingbao, 1987

Genus *Decolya* Bolivar, 1900

Subgenus *Decolya* Bolivar, 1900

335. Decolya (Decolya) visenda Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).
Subfamily **MECONEMATINAE** Burmeister, 1838

Tribe **Meconematini** Burmeister, 1838

Genus *Indokuzicus* Gorochov, 1998

336. Indokuzicus militaris (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Genus *Kuzicus* Gorochov, 1993

Subgenus *Parakuzicus* Ingrisch & Shishodia, 2000

337. Kuzicus (Parakuzicus) cervicus Ingrisch & Shishodia, 2000

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (North Aarkadu district: Kottur).

338. Kuzicus (Parakuzicus) excavatus Ingrisch & Shishodia, 2000

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kolli Hills).

339. Kuzicus (Parakuzicus) forficatus (Bolivar, 1900)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Genus *Nicephora* Bolivar, 1900

Subgenus *Dianicephora* Gorochov, 1993

340. Nicephora (Dianicephora) mirabilis Gorochov, 1993

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).

Subgenus *Nicephora* Bolivar, 1900

- 341. *Nicephora (Nicephora) mazerani*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).
- 342. *Nicephora (Nicephora) subulata*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).
- 343. *Nicephora (Nicephora) trigonioides*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).
 Genus *Thaumaspis* Bolivar, 1900
 Subgenus *Isothaumaspis* Gorochov, 1993
- 344. *Thaumaspis (Isothaumaspis) forcipatus*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).
 Subgenus *Thaumaspis* Bolivar, 1900
- 345. *Thaumaspis (Thaumaspis) castetsi*** Gorochov, 1993
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).
- 346. *Thaumaspis (Thaumaspis) longipes*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).
- 347. *Thaumaspis (Thaumaspis) trigonurus*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).
 Genus *Xiphidiopsis* Redtenbacher, 1891
 Subgenus *Xiphidiopsis* Redtenbacher, 1891
- 348. *Xiphidiopsis (Xiphidiopsis) ocellata*** Bei-Bienko, 1971
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Coimbatore district: Aanaimalai Hills).
 Subgenus *Xiphidiopsis* Redtenbacher, 1891
- 349. *Xiphidiopsis (Xiphidiopsis) straminula*** Walker, 1871
Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.
Elsewhere: Java and Sri Lanka.
 Genus *Xizicus* Gorochov, 1993
 Subgenus *Eoxizicus* Gorochov, 1993
- 350. *Xizicus (Eoxizicus) simplicicercis*** (Kevan & Jin, 1993)
Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.
 Subfamily **MECOPODINAE** Walker, 1871
 Tribe **Mecopodini** Walker, 1871
 Genus *Mecopoda* Serville, 1831
- 351* *Mecopoda elongata elongata* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.
Elsewhere: Australia, Aru Islands, Borneo, Celebes, China, Indonesia, Japan, Malacca, Malaysia, Moluccas, New Guinea, Philippines, Singapore, Sunda Islands, Taiwan, Thailand and Tonkin.
 Subfamily **PHENEROPTERINAE** Burmeister, 1838
 Genus *Himertula* Uvarov, 1940
- 352. *Himertula vidhyavathiae*** Ingrisch & Muralirangan, 2003
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.
 Genus *Letana* Walker, 1869
- 353. *Letana atomifera*** (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878)
Distribution: India: Karnataka, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.
Elsewhere: Nepal.
- 354. *Letana bulbosa*** Ingrisch, 1990
Distribution: India: Karnataka, Kerala, Pudhucherry, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.
- 355. *Letana inflata*** (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878)
Distribution: India: Delhi and Tamil Nadu.
Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.
- 356. *Letana infurcata*** Ingrisch, 1990
Distribution: India: Madhya Pradesh, Pudhucherry (Nedungadu) and Tamil Nadu (Thanjavur district).
- 357. *Letana megastridula*** Ingrisch, 1990
Distribution: India: Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu (Shervarayan Hills and Yerkadu Hills).
 Genus *Molpa* Walker, 1870
- 358. *Molpa spatulata*** (Bolivar, 1990)
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Kodaikanal).
 Genus *Niphella* Bolivar, 1900
- 359. *Niphella pulchra*** Bolivar, 1900
Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Madurai district).
 Tribe **Elimaeini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1891
 Genus *Elimaea* Stål, 1874

Subgenus *Elimaea* Stål, 1874

360. *Elimaea (Elimaea) melanocantha* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Indonesia, Malaysia, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

361. *Elimaea (Elimaea) securigera* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1891

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Indonesia, Java, Nepal, Philippines and Sri Lanka.

Subgenus *Rhaebelimaea* Ingrisch, 1990

362. *Elimaea (Rhaebelimaea) nigrosignata* Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Dhindukkal and Madurai districts).

Genus *Orthelimaea* Karny, 1926

363. *Orthelimaea carispina* Ingrisch & Shishodia, 1998

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Krishnagiri district: Thali, Jawalagiri).

Tribe *Ducetini* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878

Genus *Ducetia* Stål, 1874

364. *Ducetia japonica* (Thunberg, 1815)

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Bangladesh, Borneo, China, Formosa, Hainan, Indo-China, Japan, Java, Kuala Lumpur, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Pakistan, Philippines, Selangor, Singapore, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, South & East Asia, Thailand, Tibet and Tonkin.

Tribe *Holochlorini* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878

Genus *Holochlora* Stål, 1873

365. * *Holochlora albida* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Malaysia and Singapore.

366. *Holochlora biloba* Stål, 1874

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

367. *Holochlora indica* Kirby, 1906

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Java and Sri Lanka.

368. *Holochlora spectabilis* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Pelerinus* Bolivar, 1906

369. *Pelerinus alienus* (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1878)

Distribution: India: Assam, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Pinang and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Tapiena* Bolivar, 1906

370. *Tapiena latifolia* Ingrisch & Shishodia, 2000

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu (Thirunelveli district).

Tribe *Phaneropterini* Burmeister, 1838

Genus *Phaneroptera* Serville, 1831

Subgenus *Phaneroptera* Serville, 1831

371. * *Phaneroptera (Phaneroptera) gracilis gracilis* Burmeister, 1838

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: Africa, Annam, Australia, Celebes, China, Indo-China, Java, Malaysia, Maldives Islands, Myanmar, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Sumba.

372. *Phaneroptera (Phaneroptera) myllocerca* Ragge, 1956

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Elsewhere: China and Myanmar.

Tribe *Trogonocoryphini* Bei-Bienko, 1954

Genus *Trigonocorypha* Stål, 1874

373. *Trigonocorypha unicolor* Stoll, 1787

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Java and Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **PSEUDOPHYLLINAE** Burmeister, 1838

Tribe **Phyllomimini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1895

Genus *Acanthoprion* Pictet & Saussure, 1892

374. *Acanthoprion suspectum* (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1895)

Distribution: India: Kerala, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Brochopeplus* Pictet & Saussure, 1892

375. *Brochopeplus exaltus* Walker, 1869

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Sri Lanka.

Genus *Paramorsimus* Beier, 1954

376. **Paramorsimus olifolius* (Fabricius, 1793)

Distribution: India: Maharashtra, Odisha and Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Malaysia and Sri Lanka.

Genus *Phyllomimus* Stål, 1873

Subgenus *Phyllomimus* Stål, 1873

377. *Phyllomimus (Phyllomimus) nodulosus*

Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Phyllozelus* Redtenbacher, 1892

Subgenus *Phyllozelus* Redtenbacher, 1892

378. *Phyllozelus (Phyllozelus) siccus siccus* (Walker, 1869)

Distribution: India: Assam, Sikkim and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Pirmeda* Henry, 1940

379. *Pirmeda rosetta* Henry, 1940

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu Coimbatore district: Poluvampatty valley between Siruvani and Muthikulam).

Tribe **Callimenellini** Gorochof, 1990

Genus *Callimenellus* Walker, 1871

380. *Callimenellus apterus* Beier, 1944

Distribution: India: Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu.

Genus *Climacoptera* Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1895

381. *Climacoptera superba* Bolivar, 1900

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Elsewhere: Java and Malaysia.

Genus *Sathrophyllia* Stål, 1874

382. *Sathrophyllia femorata* (Fabricius, 1787 and Pawara et al, 2014)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Maharashtra, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Borneo, Cambodia, Java, Malaysia, Myanmar and Sumatra.

383. *Sathrophyllia fuliginosa fuliginosa* Stål, 1874

Distribution: India: Odisha and Tamil Nadu (Chennai district: Ghindy Reserve Forest).

Elsewhere: Nepal.

384. *Sathrophyllia rugosa* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Java, Sri Lanka and Sumatra.

SUMMARY

Out of this 384 species identified in Tamil Nadu there are about 115 species are endemic.

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